

Microfluidic systems in CubeSats: State of the art and its application in the BIXO mission

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Abstract

Microfluidic systems are an indispensable part of bacteriological experiments carried out inside nanosatellites, since the growth medium needed to feed the biologic organisms is pumped along them. BIXO, Bacteriological Intercommunication eXperiment in Orbit, is the mission developed by the UVigo Spacelab team that will conduct an experiment involving *Chromobacterium violaceum*, a bacteria that segregates a violet pigment when it establishes contact with cells from another colony. This process is called Quorum Sensing (QS) and the behaviour of the colonies can be studied through the light absorbance level evolution resulting from it. For this purpose, a microfluidic system will be placed inside the Pressure Vessel (PV) in order to store, pump and control the nutrient-rich liquid that will activate the growth process of *C. violaceum* at three different times during the nine-month duration of the mission.

During the first section of this paper, several microfluidic architectures from previous biological CubeSat missions will be discussed. Although there is little scientific literature concerning microfluidics in space, information collected from eight different biological experiments performed inside nanosatellites provides extraordinary knowledge and huge experience transfer in the development of this equipment. Some of these missions include EcAMSat and BioSen-

tinel, by NASA; Spacedot, from the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki; and Morebac, from the KTH Royal Institute of Technology.

Finally, the configuration and design of the microfluidic system that will be mounted inside BIXO's PV will be justified in accordance with the information previously gathered. Nevertheless, it is important to keep in mind that, when designing an equipment like this, the optimal architectural configuration is the one that better fits the requirements of the mission, therefore some decisions were taken considering not only the scientific literature but also the particular characteristics of BIXO.

1 Introduction

The space sector has historically remained inaccessible to the majority of people due to its exorbitant production costs since its inception. This *statu quo* completely changed after the arise of the CubeSat Standard, which facilitated the entry of universities, companies and other interested actors into the space sector.

In this context, the BIXO mission arises as a student project with the goal of extending the knowledge on bacterial communication under spaceflight conditions [1]. To this aim, *C. violaceum* samples will be exposed to radiation and microgravity, the impact of

which will be measured in three batches separated in a period of nine months. Each of these batches will be separately stored and preserved until the beginning of the experiment in a freeze-dried state. Once the experiment takes place, the lyophiles must be re-hydrated in order to reactivate its metabolic activity and get the QS to start.

As a consequence of the experimental procedure, and as with all biological CubeSat missions performed before, a microfluidic system is needed to take the bacteria out of the freeze-dried state as well as to provide the growth medium and drive them up to the Lab on a Chip (LoC) wells where light absorbance will be measured. Despite *C. violaceum* being an anaerobic cell, the production of violacein - the segregated violet pigment - directly depends on the presence of oxygen. Ought to this, atmospheric-like ambient conditions will be kept inside the PV where the whole microfluidic system will be stored.

Regarding the uniqueness of the BIXO mission, it is the first biological experiment to be performed inside a CubeSat as small as a 2U (20x10x10 cm). This means that the microfluidic systems from previous missions involving bacteria or other forms of life had less strict size constraints. Nevertheless, there is much expertise and knowledge to be extracted from these and thus the analysis of their architecture and operating principles is crucial for the design of BIXO's microfluidic system.

2 State of the Art

For the last two decades, biological CubeSats have experienced a significant development as a result of the multiple missions NASA has carried out during this time. Specifically, five biological experiments have been performed to study space effects in Low Earth Orbit (LEO): GeneSat-1 (2006), PharmaSat (2009), O/OREOS SESLO (2010), SporeSat (2014) and EcAMSat (2017). In addition, there is another CubeSat mission being executed at the moment, called BioSentinel (2022), which aims to travel beyond LEO and reach an heliocentric orbit in order to quantify the impact of deep space radiation on living microorganisms. In each of these CubeSats, the

Figure 1: The pressurized payload volume and optical bench of GeneSat-1 (image credit: NASA/ARC)

design of the microfluidic system implemented was enhanced over the previous one.

Apart from this series of biological missions performed by NASA, there are other educational projects, like AcubeSAT or MOREBAC, aiming to perform experiments on organisms in spaceflight conditions to assess the effects of microgravity and long exposure to radiation.

2.1 GeneSat-1

The first biological payload launched to space inside a CubeSat was GeneSat-1, whose main objective was to study the effects of microgravity on gene expression in two strains of *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) modified to produce GFP, a green fluorescent protein [2]. Two thirds of the volume of this 3U CubeSat were occupied by a pressurized sealed vessel with a cylindrical shape, inside which the integrated fluidics, optical sensors, electrical and mechanical subsystems, internal heaters and controllers were placed, as seen in Figure 1.

As for the fluidic system, it consisted on an acrylic microfluidic plate (Figure 2) that implemented 12 wells of 110 μL each, 10 of which for cul-

Figure 2: GeneSat-1's Microwell Plate [2]

ture, designed to be evenly filled from the single inlet channel and the other 2 for solid-state references. Each of the culture wells was equipped with two 0.5- μm -porosity nylon membrane filters at the inlet and outlet ports in order to maintain the *E. coli* cells inside them while the growth medium was pumped, which was the only in-space operation performed by the microfluidic system [3]. This was necessary to substitute the stasis medium, in which the bacteria were embedded and preserved, with nutrient medium to guarantee their development.

Regarding the plate, it was composed of multiple laser-cut acrylic layers attached together with pressure-sensitive adhesive interlayers. The bottom surface of the plate was as thin as 0.5 mm to ensure optical quality, since the gene expression of the bacteria was measured via a sophisticated blue-LED-excited fluorescent detection system that quantified the levels of light emitted by GFP. Figure 3 shows the subassembly of the individual optical detector system dedicated for each well.

Attending other components of the system, the bag/pump unit was composed of a 15 mL medical-grade polyethylene vinyl (PEVA) bag filled with nutrient medium and a helical spring making pressure in it. Another empty PEVA bag was attached to the outlet of the fluidic system in order to collect waste and surplus air.

As for the thermal regulation, two custom Kap-

Figure 3: Scheme of the integrated optical detector system for Genesat-1(image credit: NASA/ARC)

ton film heaters together with an array of six temperature sensors were used under a closed-loop control. The sensors were located over black-anodized aluminium plates that worked as thermal spreaders. A remote command triggered the experiment 49 h after the launch to bring the card temperature from - approximately - 10 °C to 34 °C, the actual operating temperature. One hour for temperature estabilization was left before a solenoid valve was automatically opened to deliver Luria Bertani (LB) growth medium plus 2.4 mg/mg/mL of carbenicillin antibiotic. Although first light scattering measurements occurred 2.8 h after the beginning of the experiment, it was not earlier than 10 h past that all microwells containing *E. coli* showed measurable growth. Finally, 100 h of measurements were necessary for extracting all data.

2.2 PharmaSat

On May 19, 2009, the PharmaSat spacecraft was launched from Wallops Flight Facility, Virginia, USA. This 5,1 kg 3U CubeSat took off from Earth with five scientific objectives to accomplish:

1. Provide life support in the form of sugars con-

Figure 4: PharmaSat's payload frame and insulation-wrapped containment vessel containing the integrated culturing and bioanalytical system [5].

sumed by the yeast, and environmental control such as temperature for yeast growth in 48 independent micro-wells.

2. Administer three groups of growing yeast with three distinct dosage levels of an antifungal agent, and one control yeast group with no dosage.
3. Track the population density and health of the yeast culture before, during and after the antifungal administration throughout optical density and Alamar Blue (AB), a dyeing agent.
4. Send the experiment and system status data extracted to Earth for analysis.
5. Measure and determine the effects of microgravity on budding yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* resistance to antifungal agent [4].

Inside this spacecraft, a 1,2 L (internal volume) gold containment vessel, as seen in Figure 4, housed the bio/fluidic, optical and thermal systems, as well as sensors and payload electronics subsystems.

The core component of the payload was a 4 x 8 in microfluidic chip, which included forty-eight 100 μ L wells for culture - distributed in four independent banks of 12 wells, each 4 mm in diameter and

7,8 mm deep and with an integrated pair of 1,2 μ m pore-size nylon fiber membrane filters to confine the yeast cells inside. Apart from those, eleven solid-state wells contained colored polymers to be used as absorbance standards [3]. The card was fabricated by Micronics Inc. from laser-cut polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) layers, glued together the same way as GeneSat-1, using a pressure-sensitive acrylic adhesive for interlayers, which were supported on polyethylene terephthalate (PET) carrier films [5]. As with GeneSat-1, a 51- μ m-thick layer of optical-quality polystyrene was placed covering the top and bottom of the fluidic card to ensure optical transparency for the three different color absorbance measurements. An exploded view of the multilayer assembly that compounds the microfluidic card is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Scheme of the integrated optical detector system for Genesat-1(image credit: NASA/ARC)

Due to the dependence on diffusion for medium mixing in microgravity, fluidic cards were designed to have the entrance and exit of fluids diagonally opposite one another, thus reducing the distance travelled to get the medium mixed.

As for the rest of the components, the microfluidic system was composed of 14 solenoid-operated three way valves from The Lee Co., a piston-type metering pump from the same brand used for precisely diluting the antifungal at 3 concentrations, a diaphragm-based pump (KNF Neuberger) used for circulation and mixing, medical connecting tub-

ing (Sanipure 60, Saint-Gobain Performance Plastics) and nine medical grade fluoropolymer bags (American Fluoroseal/Saint Gobain) used for storing growth medium, AB viability dye, antifungal agent (Voriconazole) and waste. In addition to utilizing Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) components, the system incorporated in-house developed elements, such as a bubble trap. Working in conjunction with four partially filled waste bags, one for each bank of wells, this bubble-suppressing mechanism played a crucial role. These bags contained a stasis buffer, responsible for maintaining a low "back pressure" and effectively preventing bubble formation caused by water evaporation.

The microfluidic system was responsible for storing the organism in its dormancy state during the pre-flight, launch and deployment period; for supplying the growth medium after reaching a stable orbit to initiate organism growth, and for mixing, metering and supplying the antifungal agent at three concentrations [5].

Six weeks prior to the nominal launch date, the inoculation of microwells with yeast cells and fluid filling of reservoir bags, tubing, channels and wells were carried out under sterile conditions [6]. The biowells were inoculated an amount of 10 μ L of a mixture of dormant *S. cerevisiae* and distilled water, with a density between 5×10^5 and 10×10^5 organisms/mL. Special attention was paid not to wet the filter membranes during this process and to avoid gas bubbles inside any tube, channel or well, so they were all purged with CO₂. Approximately 2 days after launch, the experiment was started throughout the raise of the microfluidic plate temperature to 27 °C. After being fed with AB-containing growth medium, the yeast cells were allowed to grow for 10,4 hours in order to recover from stasis. Voriconazole was then pumped into each of the four rows of wells; three of them with different concentrations and the other was left as a control. Color changes of AB due to metabolic activity were measured for 72 h in separated periods of 15 min [6].

Regarding the optical system in charge of quantifying the color changes, each of the 48 culture wells and 11 solid-state reference wells had an optical sub-assembly of 3 color LED's emitting at 470, 525 and

615 nm. Cell growth was measured in two ways: optical density changes ought to light scattering by *S. cerevisiae* cells, directly proportional to the cell population; and color change of the AB dye, which switched from blue (oxidized form) to pink (reduced form) as a result of enzymes generated because of the metabolic processes acting upon it. Data extracted from the experiment showed that blue AB had its peak at 600 nm while pink AB had its peak at 570 nm. As for the three LED colors, the red one tracked the concentration of the oxidized form of AB (blue), the green was sensitive to the reduced form of AB (pink) and the blue one did not match strongly to the absorbance of any form of it, so it responded to light scattering. Figure 6 shows uncorrected (left) and corrected (right) light absorbances for the laboratory growth of *S. cerevisiae* in one well of the fluidics card. Reasonable estimations of cell number and concentration of any AB form can be extracted from the corrected data [6].

The thermal display of the system was very similar to the previous one from GeneSat-1, composed of a pair of Kapton-film heaters glued to 3 mm anodized black aluminium plates.

2.3 O/OREOS

Just a year after Pharmasat's launch, O/OREOS (Organism/Organic Exposure to Orbital Stresses) settled the record for the first autonomous satellite to perform two independent experiments. The first of them, SESLO (Space Environment Survivability of Living Organisms), analysed how LEO radiation and microgravity affected the spores of *Bacillus subtilis*. SEVO (Space Environment Viability of Organics), the other payload, investigated the photodegradation of biomarkers and bio-building blocks via UV-visible spectroscopy[3]. This satellite was aimed to the highest inclination (72°), 650 km Earth orbit, where it was exposed to the inner Van Allen rings, known for the presence of trapped particle radiation and higher exposure to galactic cosmic rays. Ought to the increased mission duration and harsher radiation environment, design considerations were taken in order to reduce risk by adding fault recovery measures, more controllability and increasing the radiation shielding

Figure 6: Three-color absorbance of one microwell of growing yeast measured with the PharmaSat optical system. Left: As-measured absorbances, corrected for known absorbance of initial concentration of blue form of alamar blue. Right: Absorbances after correction for “cross terms”, resulting in absorbances of the two forms of AB and the optical density due to light scattering by the yeast cells [6].

[7].

Figure 7: The O/OREOS Nanosatellite [7].

The capability to carry two independent and interchangeable payloads in a 3U volume is the main feature of the O/OREOS technology demonstration. Autonomous stand-alone packages containing the electronics, microcontroller and data storage were included inside each payload.

O/OREOS’s SESLO payload contained a pair of strains of two organisms: *Halorubrum chaoviatoris* and *Bacillus subtilis* spores. Both were dried and sealed at 1 atm (internal pressure) and laboratory-

ambient humidity. The payload was composed of three modules (Figure 8), each of them including an array of twelve 75- μ L microfluidic wells [3]. In order to ensure stasis of the biological organisms, they were loaded into the modules after being air dried. When the spacecraft reached a stable orbit, the rehydration process took place, causing viable cells to resume their growth and reproduction. Each of the three modules was rehydrated at three different time-points to study the effects of the cumulative radiation dose. The first module was rehydrated right after the launch, while the second and third modules waited three and six months more to be rehydrated, respectively. As a result, the differences in growth patterns were attributed to the different amount of radiation absorbed prior to rehydration [7].

Each “bioblock” module contained an assembly of reservoirs, microfluidic channels, sensor and solenoid valves, aimed to control the flow of the growth media to the biological specimens located in the wells. The flow was produced by a diaphragm air pump, which exerted pressure on elastomeric membranes that pushed the spore germination medium and AB reservoirs contained inside the module. Membranes of gas-permeable material cov-

Figure 8: O/OREOS SESLO Sample Modules [7].

ered the microwells to guarantee the exchange of oxygen and carbon dioxide during cell growth. In order to achieve longer periods of stasis, desiccated biology with demonstrated survival of eight months was a significant development for the NASA team.

Regarding the tracking of the cell growth, a 3-color LED illumination system similar to the one used in PharmaSat was utilized to monitor spore germination, cell growth and metabolic activity. The data was extracted during 48 h periods of time repeated at the three different timepoints.

As a result of the higher inclination orbit (650 km above Earth; 72°) compared to GeneSat1 and PharmaSat (450 km; 40°), together with a lower thickness of the aluminium PV wall closer to the samples, 15x higher ionizing radiation doses were absorbed by the biological samples, as radiation-sensitive field-effect transistors (radFETs) detected [3],[7].

On the other hand, the second payload, SEVO, conducted an experiment that investigated the stability, modification and degradation of organic molecules in thin-film form, simulating the conditions of 4 environments: interplanetary/interstellar space, the lunar surface, wet/salty environments and the Martian atmosphere. UV-visible spectroscopy was used to periodically monitor the chemical consequences of exposing these films to solar UV, visible light and space ionizing radiation. However, to per-

form this experiment no fluidic system was needed and therefore the rest of the payload description is not relevant to BIXO's payload development.

2.4 SporeSat

The SporeSat mission was an autonomous, free-flying 3U spacecraft launched in 2014 (330 km above Earth; 51,6°) used to conduct scientific experiments to expand the knowledge of the mechanisms of plant cell gravity sensing. Specifically, the experiment investigated the effects on the reproductive spores of the fern, *Ceraptoteris richardii*, since plants like this use gravity to determine direction and to guide their roots to grow down into the earth to find nutrients [3, 8].

Alike O/OREOS SEVO, the payload of the SporeSat mission did not involve an active fluidic system and thus the description of the experiment will not be thoroughly extended. Nevertheless, this spacecraft was the first CubeSat to use lab-on-a-chip devices [3], called biology compact discs (bioCDs). BioCD was the name given to a 50 mm-diameter fused silica disc that included ion-selective electrode (ISE) pairs to measure calcium ion activity during spore germination under rotation. Each of the three bioCDs accommodated up to 32 spores arranged at four different radii of rotation with a photodefined epoxy (SU-8) holding structure. As a result, four different levels of simulated centrifugal gravity were achieved by rotating one disk [9]. Two of the bioCDs rotated onboard using minicentrifuges while the third stayed stationary as a microgravity control [3]. The temperature inside the payload was regulated thanks to four Pt-film resistance temperature detectors (RTDs) placed along the outermost radius of rotation of the disks and exposed to the same volume of germination medium as contained in the spore wells. These sensors accurately indicated the spore temperature achieved via heaters [9].

Loading the spores onto bioCDs was a task performed under green safelight to prevent premature germination. The process to individually insert the spores suspended in ultrapure water into each well demanded a custom capillary micromanipulator and a stereo microscope with 40x magnification.

Figure 9: Exploded view of the SporeSat (image credit: NASA)

After that, 20 μL of additional 2% agar germination medium were introduced into each well. The next step was to take an image of every well to ensure that spores had been properly inserted into the bioCD, no air bubbles were trapped inside and ion-selective membranes had been completely wetted. Finally, the three bioCDs were attached and the rotating structure was sealed. This assembly remained into complete darkness for 3-6 days before the experiment began [9].

Overall, the mission successfully demonstrated the use of ISEs and artificial gravity technologies in LEO, though the red LED lights intended for spore germination failed on the ground and during space-flight [3].

2.5 EcAMSat

The *E. coli* AntiMicrobial Satellite (*EcAMSat*) was a successful spaceflight mission developed by NASA Ames Research Center as part of a series of biology-focused CubeSats (in which previously mentioned satellites are included), and that performed an autonomous experiment to investigate the effects on microgravity on the antibiotic resistance of uropathogenic *E. coli* [10]. Actually, the EcAMSat payload was a re-flight of PharmaSat's payload hard-

Figure 10: Exploded view and photo of prototype of the Lab-on-a-Chip (bioCD) Rotating Assembly that contains and measures the fern spores (image credit: PU, NASA).

ware (both satellites share 90% of their features) and both missions shared similarities in their requirements: studying the effect of microgravity on the response of microorganisms to drugs used to kill them. Nevertheless, several changes had to be applied to PharmaSat's experiment protocol to adjust for the

differences between yeast cells and *E. coli*. For example, yeast cells were stored in distilled water as a stasis medium until the system reached the experiment temperature, whereas *E. coli* were stored in M9 buffer, a "minimal salts" medium containing: 22 mM KH_2PO_4 ; 42 mM Na_2HPO_2 ; 8.5 mM NaCl ; 19 mM NH_4Cl ; 1 mM MgSO_4 and 0.01 mM CaCl_2 . Instead of growth medium with 10% of AB, LB growth medium was directly pumped to the fluidic card after reaching the nominal experiment temperature. Cells were then allowed to grow to stationary phase and remain there for 24 h. After that, a bank of wells used as control received a dose of M9. In order to achieve different doses of gentamicin (Gm) a metering pump was used to extract precise amounts of this antibiotic from the bag where it was stored. Another diaphragm pump was then in charge of pumping the drawn fluid along a loop circuit that included the M9 reservoir. For better understanding of the process, Figure 11 can be consulted. Once incubation with the different Gm dose levels had occurred, 10% AB in buffer was added and the cell metabolism was monitored for a period of 48 h [10].

Although EcAMSat was the first 6U biological CubeSat, the size of the payload remained a 2U, like PharmaSat, due to the rest of the volume being dedicated to the bus (1U) and hysteresis rods and magnets (3U). In addition, the greater surface of the spacecraft allowed bigger solar panels to be installed and therefore supply the necessary power to increase by 10 °C the temperature of the payload (EcAMSat: 37 °C; PharmaSat: 27 °C) [10, 3].

Concerning the detailed description of the components of the system, a valve board assembled a series of electrovalves from The Lee Company, specifically the LHDA0533315H model, a 5 V-supplied solenoid valve of 3 ports. Prior to each use, fresh Sanipure BDF silicone tubing from Saint-Gobain was connected to the ports of these valves. Afterwards, a custom spring was placed around the tubes attachments to apply higher adhesion force. To store all the reagents, custom-sized bags of FEP (Fluorinated Ethylene Propylene; Saint-Gobain) with a capacity between 25 and 35 ml were filled through an L-shaped dipstick. Some of them were partially filled to produce some backpressure and thus prevent bubble for-

mation. To move the fluid along the system, two pumps were used: the KNF NF5 diaphragm pump and the Lee Co. LPV series metering pump. The first one was used for priming the valves with the appropriate amount of fluid before delivering it to the card, while the stepper-motor-driven pump was used for controlling the volume pumped to the card, as it had a 100 nl/step resolution. A relevant feature of the system was the use of a bubble trap to prevent gas bubbles from reaching the fluidic chips. This custom made device placed between the pump and the fluidic chip was made of a stack of silicone that defined the flow path through two porous polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) membrane filters of 0,2 μm pore and a stainless steel mesh screen. Because of the inner channelling of the device, the bubbles were forced to pass through the pores of the membranes while the hydrophobic filter prevented the fluid from escaping [10].

The microfluidic chip was based on PharmaSat's design, as it also contained four rows of twelve 100 μl microwells each, however, the reference wells were left unused. On top and bottom of these 4-mm-diameter wells, the same 50- μm polystyrene layer used in GeneSat-1 and PharmaSat was placed to ensure oxygen exchange for cell growth. The position of the inlets and outlets of the wells were also strategically positioned to improve the liquid mixing due to diffusion lengths consistence throughout the wells. The same laser cut and Pressure Sensitive Adhesive (PSA) gluing process was followed to produce these PMMA cards. Overall, 19 layers and 96 hand-aligned filters were part of these chips. The pore size of the membrane filters had to be reduced from 1,2 μm down to 0,2 μm ought to the fact that *E. coli* cells are around five times smaller than yeast cells.

The thermal regulation system was the same as described in previous biological missions from NASA.

2.6 BioSentinel

On the 16th of November 2022, the Artemis-1 mission successfully took off, carrying aboard a secondary payload, the BioSentinel satellite, aimed to orbit around the Sun for about 6 - 12 months [12]. This means that it will be the first interplanetary

Figure 11: Schematic diagram of EcAMSat fluidic system [11]

biological CubeSat and the first live-biology experiment conducted beyond the Earth-Moon system [12]. During this period, the biological satellite will investigate the effects of deep space ionizing radiation on living organisms. To achieve this goal, budding yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) cells were chosen not only because of the ease of genetic manipulation, but also because of their similarity to human cells, even in DSB (Double Stranded Breaks) reparation, which are DNA lesions that can cause cancer in humans if not properly treated [13]. In addition, desiccated yeast cells are proven to survive for long periods of time in that preservation state, what makes them really suitable for spaceflights since schedules tend to be delayed. Two strains of *S. cerevisiae* will be part of the experiment: a wild type strain, used for control of yeast health; and a *rad51* deletion strain, which is defective for DNA damage repair and will show

metabolic and growth deficits caused by radiation damage. Although similar amounts of radiation will be absorbed by both samples, the wild type one is expected to be much more effective in healing the damage.

Inside the payload, there are 18 fluidic cards with a total number of 16 microwells (100 μ l) containing dried yeast samples. Each of the 288 wells counts with a pair of filter membranes and inlet and outlet microchannels. For nine times during the 6 month nominal mission, a pair of fluidic cards will be rehydrated simultaneously by pumping Synthetic Complete (SC) growth medium and AB to the samples inside. Another copy of the payload (the BioSensor) will be launched to the ISS and a third one will stay on Earth. The comparison between data extracted from each of the three environments will be analysed later to assess the impact of dose and particle depen-

Figure 12: Side view diagram of one of the microwells inside EcAMSat fluidic chip [10].

dent radiation damage on biological systems in the form of DBSs [12].

For the first time in a NASA biological CubeSat, microfluidic chips are made of polycarbonate (PC), specifically, two PC layers assembled together using PSA. The resulting dimensions of the chips are 39 x 41 x 13 mm. At the outlet of each well there is a 1 μm -size polycarbonate track-etched (PCTE) filter that prevents the yeast cells from escaping out of them. Before completely assembling the multiple layers of the chips, the yeast cells are loaded onto the sidewall of each well and allowed to dry for 7 days. Another filter of the same material, of 0,2 μm pore size, is then located in the inlet of the well and the whole card is pressed with a pneumatic press [12].

The 18 fluidic cards contained inside the BioSensor are subdivided in two independent halves controlled by an independent card manifold. When any of the 3-way valves is actioned, it drives the flow to the corresponding fluidic card.

Separated from these components, inside the "bag box", are located the FEP bags containing the SC and the AB and the peristaltic pumps. Another manifold, known as the "bag manifold" is then used for connecting the bags with the card manifolds.

Temperature regulation during the stasis phase builds on the thermal system implemented by

GeneSat-1, PharmaSat and EcAMSat: kapton-film heaters and aluminum thermal spreaders.

2.7 AcubeSAT

The AcubeSAT mission is the first of the mentioned to not be part of NASA's series of CubeSats for biological research in space conditions. The main goals of the mission are the following:

- Generate systematic view of the yeast proteome in flux in unprecedented scale for space missions.
- Prove effects of microgravity and radiation on eukaryotic cells.
- Conduct research on extraterrestrial applicable biotechnology and space-related pathogenesis.
- Demonstrate that Lab-on-a-Chip (LOC) technologies can be reliably employed aboard CubeSats for multiplexing of experiments.

In contrast to the missions mentioned before, the AcubeSAT uses Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) silicone for microfluidic chips crafting instead of PMMA or PC. The chips are composed of two layers: control and flow; therefore two moulds have to be fabricated (by photolithography). The first one consists of channels of a height of 14 μl while the second ones have a height of 30 μl . The flow layer can be filled with an approximated volume of 10-20 μl . The final dimensions of the microfluidic chips are 45 x 29 x 10 mm.

Apart from the fluidic chips, the system is composed of 2 positive displacement pumps; 14 solenoid valves (8 latching for the flow layer and 6 non-latching for control layer); and 3 bags acting as containers for the growth medium, distilled water and waste. All of them are made of FEP, a fluoropolymer that presents chemical and biological inertness and wide thermal operation range.

The pumps are used for creating the pressure needed for controlling the on-chip micro-valves and flow layers. Both of them are HPN Mikrosysteme mzt-2921, whose pump heads have been proved aboard the ISS. The working pressure of the pump

Figure 13: (A) The card manifold, showing the valves, bubble traps, and the desiccant assemblies for each card position. (B) The assembled card box (minus gap pads) showing the 18 cards and 2 calibration cells installed. (C) The bag manifold with calibration cell, pump, valves, and FEP tubing. (D) The assembled bag box, with two manifolds, FEP fluidic bags, kapton heaters, and RTDs [12].

is up to 300 kPa and the speed rate is between 1 and 3000 RPM, with the minimum flow rate of the selected pump being $0,003 \mu\text{l}/\text{min}$

On the other hand, the solenoid valves are used for three main purposes: to control the flow inside the flow layer (flow valves); to control the flow inside the control layer, or controlling the on-chip microvalves (control valves); and to evenly distribute the fluid among different areas. The model selected for flow valves is the LHLA0542311H, a 2-port latching solenoid valve from Lee Co., while the LHDA0523312H model was chosen as the control valve, which are the same conventional 3-port valve that flew aboard EcAMSat but with different ports.

Valves will be operated in a non-conventional way by inverting the inlet and outlet ports and thus using the Normally Closed port as an inlet.

Ought to the necessity of a platform that integrates all the valves in a compact form, minimizes connections, simplifies assembly, and achieves higher structural resistance, an in-house-designed manifold was used. It was manufactured in PEEK on a conventional 3-axis milling machine [14].

2.8 MOREBAC

MOREBAC is one of the eight payloads the MIST 3U Cubesat would house aboard, as a result

Figure 14: 3D diagram of the fluidic chip. In green flow layer and in blue control layer [14].

Figure 15: Valve manifold assembly, with integrated flow and control valves [14]

of a project collaboration between the KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm University and Uppsala University. As it is stated by their developers: "the purpose of the MOREBAC experiment is to build a smaller experiment platform than earlier bacteria experiments in space and to attempt resus-

citation" [15].

Based on the review of other missions, the architecture of the MOREBAC fluidic system simply involves a spring pressurized single reservoir (a polymer bag), like the one used in GeneSat-1; four valves for driving the flow; and a waste bag as the outlet.

The nutrient medium is stored inside 6 ml FEP bags before being pumped to the wells. The fluid is pressurized by four helical springs generating a pressure of 1 atm. The medium reservoir is expected to withstand temperatures from $-200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

As for the solenoid valves, the same 3-port Lee Co electrovalves used in AcubeSAT are used, but the latching version to reduce energy consumption. These can be seen directly attached to the LoC in Figure 17.

Finally, the fluidic card contains three $31\text{ }\mu\text{l}$ wells for culture and other three wells of the same size for control. The objective of the mission is to separately test each pair of culture-v-control wells in three batches. The inlets and outlets of the wells are placed

Figure 16: Fluidic diagram of MOREBAC [15].

diagonally opposed as in Pharmasat to increase the mixing of the bacteria within the medium via diffusion. In addition, membrane filters are as well placed at each end of the wells to avoid the bacteria from getting out of them. The whole chip is made of five layers of optical transparent acrylic bonded together with adhesive, resulting in a 9 mm-thick card.

Figure 17: 3D representation of the solenoid valves and fluidic chip of MOREBAC [15].

3 BIXO mission

3.1 Main differences with previous ones

Despite the existence of several common points between BIXO and previously mentioned missions (i.e. they are biological experiments, organisms have to be preserved before the beginning of the experiment, etc.), there are also many aspects of the BIXO mission that remain unique:

1. The mission will be carried out inside a 2U Cube-Sat.
2. The experiment will be conducted on *C. violaceum*.
3. The bacteria will be preserved in a freeze-dried state.

Most of the design decisions were made with these special features in mind, so the architecture of the fluidic system may differ from others previously studied.

3.2 Mission phases

The BIXO mission protocol is subdivided into five phases that cover the operational goals from launch to the end of the mission, namely Low-Earth-Orbit-Operations (LEOP), Commissioning, Main Science, Technology Demonstration and Long storage experiment.

Firstly, during LEOP (3 days) subsystems will be initialized, antennas will be deployed and possible errors will be checked. Commissioning will begin after that, and payload sensors and actuators will be calibrated. About one or two weeks later, Main Science phase will be initialised and so will the experiment. The first step of this phase is the De-lyophilisation 1, in which the samples of normal and mutant *C. violaceum* strains will be provided with LB growth medium to reactivate their metabolism. The second step consists on the execution of Experiment Batch 1, which is started by pumping the volume of growth medium with mixed bacteria into the microwells of the fluidic cards.

When the spectrometers placed above each of the microwells confirm they have been filled, a periodical light absorbance measurement is taken to study the evolution of cellular density and violacein production. This process is performed with the normal (violacein-producing) strain and with the mutant (non-violacein-producing) strain, used as a control. The level of radiation absorbed is also registered and taken into account during the Waiting phase, when data are analysed and possible changes for the second batch may be applied. Once the modifications are performed and the waiting time is over, the second batch of bacteria can enter the De-lyophilisation 2 phase and repeat the experimental process. Data extracted from the second batch are discussed and analysed during the Technology Demonstration phase, lasting until the last month of the nominal time of the mission (9 months), and during which the camera payload and the in-house developed ADCS (Attitude Determination and Control System) will be tested. Long-Term Storage phase is then initialised, aiming to examine the impact of high radiation dosage levels resulting from nine months of exposure to cosmic radiation. To this end, the proceeding followed in Main Science phase will be repeated with the remaining batch.

3.3 Fluidic system

3.3.1 Architecture

The fluidic system aboard BIXO is responsible for two main tasks: keeping the lyophile in stasis phase while needed, and allowing the independent execution of the De-lyofilisation and Experiment batch phases at three different times with three different batches. To accomplish these objectives, the architecture of the fluidic system is designed as seen in Figure 18.

From left to right, as shown in the diagram: the liquid bag, containing the LB growth medium; the peristaltic pump, in charge of dispensing the broth to the bacteria; a series of eight solenoid valves, to redirect the flow to each of the rows of wells; eight check valves, preventing possible unwanted flow from reaching the freeze-dried bacteria due to vibrations un-

locking the electrovalves; bacteria reservoirs, half of them normal and half mutant; another set of 8 check valves, to prevent back flow from spoiling the stasis state of lyophiles in case the fluidic card is launched filled with stasis medium; a pair of fluidic cards integrating two rows of 8 microfluidic wells; another set of check valves to prevent cross contamination between samples; and a waste bag to collect the surplus broth, air, or a possible stasis medium. Apart from these components, the red box represents the manifold, a structural piece to which the pump and the electrovalves are attached and that integrates channels inside to connect these components as shown.

It is relevant to mention that neither the distribution of the wells inside the microfluidic chips nor the number of batches to study are strictly fixed parameters, ought to the fact that other displays of well-to-well channelling (i.e. parallel) have been successfully tested, and that there is enough available space for the execution of even four experiment batches.

3.3.2 Liquid and waste bags

Fluid and waste bags are a common component that most biological CubeSats have used to store growth media, antifungal broth or any other sort of liquid to be dispensed to the onboard organisms. In the case of BIXO, FEP bags were initially considered for storing LB growth medium (liquid bag), bacteria (bacteria reservoir) and leftover air and medium (waste bag); however, it was eventually discarded for storing the bacteria because of the difficulty of handling the bacterial lyophiles and integrating them into the bag. Alike BioSentinel, the manufacturer chosen for providing the FEP bags was Saint Gobain (American Fluoroseal), well known for producing these type of bags for other biosats. After carefully exploring the entirety of the company's catalogue, we concluded that KryoSure "F" bags would better fit our requirements for this component, as these bags are described as "durable, transparent and flexible storage down to liquid nitrogen temperatures", according to their manufacturer [16].

Nevertheless, in line with our dedication to cost reduction for the development of biological CubeSats and to ensure the democratization of the space sector,

Figure 18: Diagram of the architecture of the BIXO fluidic system

we are currently exploring alternative options that offer a more favorable balance between cost and quality. Alternatively, there are other possible medical bags that may not have the same experience in spaceflight missions but can guarantee the accomplishment of the requirements. After all, reservoir bags are passive components that are required no more than properly storing the growth medium and resisting slightly low temperatures (0 °C in Idle Mode).

3.3.3 Pump

The pump is considered the most critical hardware component of the fluidic system since, in case of failure, there is no redundancy and the whole experiment is spoiled. Therefore, the validation procedure of this device must be exhaustive.

Contrary to what happens with the fluid and waste bags, the offer of microfluidic pumps is much wider, even though most of the models had to be discarded due to size constraints. Some companies discussed for acquiring the pump were The Lee Com-

pany, HNP Mikrosysteme and Takasago Fluidic Systems.

The main requirements established for the pump were the following:

- The pump shall not exceed PV internal dimensions (66 x 66 x 84,5 mm)
- The pump shall resist a temperature range within 0 °C and 30 °C
- The pump shall weight less than 120 g.
- The pump shall consume less than 3 W.

After assessing many different options from each of these companies catalogs, the Takasago RP-Q III (Figure 19) peristaltic pump was selected for anticipated testing due to its reduced size, configurable volume rate and acceptable power consumption. The eccentric wheel priming the silicone tube produces a pressure within 30 and 50 kPa. The body of this component (not counting the mounting flanges) measures 15 x 17 x 32,2 mm, which is significantly less

than the dimensions of other pumps of the same company, such as the RP-HX pump (32 x 20 x 46 mm), or Lee Co's LPM series pump (61,2 x 19,8 x 15 mm). Due to its reduced volume, the weight of this device is also reduced to only 13 g. The regulation of its volume rate is possible in a range between 0,06 and 60 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ or 3 and 1100 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ (the one used in BIXO) ought to the 3 V DC stepper motor that primes the silicone tube around a driven eccentric wheel. According to the manufacturer, it consumes less than 0,36 W and the detachable head is auto-clavable, an important fact for desinfecting the piece [17].

Figure 19: The Takasago RP-Q III pump.

It is also relevant to mention that this same peristaltic pump was selected by NASA for the BioSentinel payload, as shown in Figure 20. Ought to this fact, it is possible to gain flight experience from BioSentinel and proactively identify any potential issues associated with this pump.

3.3.4 Electrovalves

As for the solenoid valves, two types of The Lee Company electrovalves were selected: the LHLA1242311H and the LHLA1252311H. Actually, both are the same device except for the housing; the first one is designed to be plugged inside the manifold

(plug-in style) while the other is screwed to connect its face to the surface of the manifold (face mount style) (Figure 21).

Among other features, the main reasons why these electrovalves seem perfect for the BIXO satellite are their magnetically latching design, optimised for ultra low power consumption (just 23 mJ/switch); their light weight, less than 2,5 g; and their minuscule size, just 6,4 x 8,3 x 19,4 mm. According to the pressure drop graphic provided by the company (Figure 22), and considering the highest possible volume rate of the pump, 1,100 mL/min, the differential pressure lost due to the valves is negligible.

As it happened with the pump, solenoid valves from The Lee Company have been widely used for fluidic systems in biological CubeSats. From EcAM-Sat to BioSentinel, passing through AcubeSAT and MIST, all these missions decided to integrate valves from this company. Indeed, the EcAMSat team concluded that the spring constants of the Lee Co. valves they used (LHDA0533315H) were sufficient for withstanding inertial loads present at the launch without momentarily opening, as they tested General Environmental Verification Standard (GEVS) GSFC-STD 7000 [10]. This is a good indication for random vibration testings that will be performed in the future on the solenoid valves that will go aboard BIXO.

3.3.5 Check valves

Other relevant components for the BIXO experiment are the check valves. These are responsible for preventing the flow of the growth medium in the undesired way and therefore avoiding cross contamination.

The Lee Company check valves were first considered for the fluidic system. Once again, several models from the catalogue were analysed and the most interesting ones ended being the CHFA1256501A (cracking pressure: $7 \pm 3,5$ kPa), CSFA1876105A (cracking pressure: $35 \pm 10,5$ kPa) and the CKFA1876201A (cracking pressure: $7 \pm 3,5$ kPa), due to all of them being specifically designed for spaceflight operations. This type of valves are thought to be directly inserted in a piece such as a manifold [19]. However, there are two main draw-

Figure 20: The Takasago RP-Q III pump and 3-port LHL Lee Co. electrovalves in BioSentinel’s payload [13].

Figure 21: LHLA1252311H (left) and LHLA1242311H (right) electrovalves.

backs coming from the use of these valves, specially considering that it is expected to integrate 24 of them in the final version of the system: the size, since the dimensions are significantly large considering the inner volume of the PV (15,7 x 4,8 x 4,8 mm), and their elevated unitary price, again taking into account our goal of democratizing the access to space, specially for educational projects like UVigo SpaceLab, with limited economical resources.

As a solution, two alternatives came up. Firstly, another check valve model designed for microfluidic application, from Bartels mikrotechnik, was found and selected for testing. This model (Figure 23) is

an in-line valve, so it is directly plugged to 1,3 mm I.D. tubing and thus no space from the manifold is dedicated for integrating them. It is made of stainless steel and silicone for sealing. The cracking pressure for forward flow is typically lower than 3,5 kPa, while the maximum back pressure supported is 50 kPa, at which a leak rate of approximately $<20 \mu\text{L}/\text{h}$ is spotted [20]. Secondly, LoC-integrated check valves were also considered for reducing the volume and price costs. Based on the work of Bessho et al.[21], the imitation of biological structures present in veins allows the integration of check valves as part of the inner channels of the microfluidic chip. The 3D model that illustrates how these biomimetic structure are applied to the design of the LoCs can be seen in Figure 24.

3.3.6 Bacteria Reservoir

As it was mentioned before, the bacteria reservoir was first thought as a polymer bag where the lyophiles could be stored until the Main Science phase began, however, the lack of bags smaller than 1 mL and the added difficulty of introducing a minuscule amount of freeze-dried bacteria led us to decide to replace it with a more suitable component. This had to accomplish some crucial requirements like being chemically inert, resisting temperatures from 0 °C to 30 °C and maintaining a dry atmosphere inside. Consequently, in response to these demands, the fluidic tanks Fluidic 639 and Fluidic 934 were chosen for testing. In spite of the different inner volume of

Figure 22: Differential pressure across the LHL valve depending on the flow rate[18].

Figure 23: Bartels microtechnik mp-cv valve [20].

Figure 24: 3D Design of a venous valve-like check valve.

both tanks (500 μL and 200 μL , respectively), these models are almost identical: made of translucent PP (polypropylene), embedded luer interface and mini-luer interface in the cap.

3.3.7 Microfluidic chip

The microfluidic chips used for BIXO are a pair of PDMS pieces, composed of two layers glued to-

gether using oxygen plasma. The thicker layer (4 mm) contains all the channelling and microwells, while the thinner one (2 mm) is completely flat.

Inside the microfluidic chips, the cell growth will be studied in 21,2 μL microwells, which are aligned with an individual set of an LED backlight and an spectrometer. For each chip, there are two rows of 8 microwells, which are subdivided into four groups:

3 wells for wild strain (violacein-producing) bacteria growth, 3 wells for mutant strain (non-violacein-producing) bacteria growth, 1 well for blank control of the LB medium and 1 well for PDMS absorbance calibration.

Figure 25: Prototype of the microfluidic chip integrating serial and parallel well distributions.

The inner channels of the chip are semi-cylindrical with a radius of 0,25 mm and can connect the microwells for bacterial growth in two different distributions: in parallel or in-series (Figure 26).

Figure 26: Comparison between in-series and in-parallel 3D designs.

Each of these possibilities presents benefits and detriments. In-parallel distribution of the wells works better for independent growth of the triplet of wells since the separation between them is greater than in-series, where microwells are interconnected by short

channels through which bacteria can easily move. This event could cause the bacteria in the middle well to grow faster than in the side wells. Alike voltage drop in electrical circuits, pressure drop in-parallel branching is lower than in-series connection of the wells, which is another important fact to take care of, specially considering other pressure drop elements present in the system like check valves. On the other hand, the main drawback of using in-parallel distribution is the possibility of not filling all the wells because of an air bubble getting stuck inside one of them while the medium flows through the others. This occurred to the KTH Royal Institute of Technology while testing MOREBAC, which observed that the fluid flowed through a single chamber before exiting the card. Due to this, they concluded that "if the system were to be redesigned it would have the wells in series" [15]. Regarding other missions, GeneSat, PharmaSat and EcAMSat implemented parallel well distribution, while BioSentinel opted for serial wells.

There are some design practices that help to reduce the possibility of issues emerging from the branching structure. One that we have applied to our chips is Murray's law, which establishes that for a parent channel (D) divided into n child channels (d), the relation between them is :

$$D^3 = \sum_{i=1}^n d_i^3$$

In addition to that, the liquid resistance of each of the three channels was matched by reducing the radius of the center (and shorter) one to 0,24 mm, as it was calculated using the online Microfluidic calculator from Elveflow [22]. As a result of applying the previous formula, the parent channel ended having a diameter of:

$$D = \sqrt[3]{2 * 0,25^3 + 0,24^3} mm$$

$$D = 0,356 mm$$

Another task the fluidic chips were expected to perform is the even mixing of the bacteria in the

growth medium before entering the wells. To this aim, a serpentine structure was placed between the inlet of the LoC and the inlet of the wells. As seen in other works (Daniel et al. [23]), this geometry is usually used for two liquid mixing, however, our goal is not to mix two liquid substances but one liquid medium and a solid (the bacteria). Because of the lack of literature about these two-states mixing, we implemented four different designs of serpentine in LoC prototypes to test which met the best our needs. They can all be seen in Figure 27

Figure 27: Four different geometries for testing of the mixing efficiency of the serpentine structure.

Concerning the production of the LoCs, the design is completely taken over by the UVigo Space-Lab (UVSL) team and developed in CATIA software, whereas the manufacturing is delegated to one of our partners, BFlow.

This last stage begins with the crafting of the mould of the channels and microfluidic wells, which is usually printed using SLA (Stereolithography) because of the reliability of the finishing. Microscope pictures of a resin-printed mould taken at the CIN-TECX (Centre for Research in Technologies, Energy

and Industrial Processes) with a Nikon SMZ25 can be seen in Figure 28.

Once the mould is printed, the PDMS is elaborated and centrifuged to prevent bubbles from appearing in the final card. Afterwards, the PDMS is introduced into a stove for four hours at 50 °C to complete the curing process. When the process has finished, it is ready to be taken out of the mould and repeat the process with the upper layer. Both layers are then glued together via oxygen plasma.

3.3.8 Manifold

The manifold is a structural part that serves as a support to fix the pump and the solenoid valves and to interconnect their ports for flow distribution. As for the BIXO fluidic system, the manifold integrates the pump and eight electrovalves; four of them plug-in and four of them face mount.

In spite of our prior intention to delegate its design and production to third part manufacturers, the costs of the process of production led us to design and manufacture it in house. Several fabrication techniques like SLA, SLS (Selective Laser Sintering) and FDM (Fused Deposition Modeling) were used for prototyping. An especial cut section of the manifold was printed using each of the previous technologies to test the dimensional quality and surface finish without consuming too much material. The results are shown in Figure 30. After thoroughly observing the pieces, we concluded that the SLA-printed was the best at dimensional accuracy, so it was chosen for printing the whole piece. The SLS prototypes resulted disappointing because of the bad resolution and detail fidelity of the final pieces while the FDM part had a better quality but still not as good as resin.

3.3.9 Heaters

As in the case of GeneSat-1, PharmaSat, O/OREOS SESLO, SporeSat, EcAMSat, BioSentinel, MOREBAC and AcubeSat, the fluidic chips are covered on both faces with a sandwich structure of heaters and aluminum thermal spreaders. In BIXO, three KHLVA-0502 heaters are attached via PSA to each of the aluminum plates to guarantee that the

Figure 28: Comparison between the dimensions of the mould (left) and the theoretical ones (right).

proper temperature for bacteria growth is delivered. The operational temperature of these polyimide insulated heaters goes from $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and their body thickness is $0,25\text{ mm}$, although it increases to $1,52\text{ mm}$ at the connector.

3.3.10 Pressure Vessel

A structural steel Pressure Vessel (PV) of estimated inner dimensions of $66 \times 66 \times 84,5\text{ mm}$ is located in the upper unit of the satellite and stores the whole microfluidic system and the PCBs for payload management. The wall thickness of the chamber is 2 mm and the pressure inside is supposed to remain between $0,8$ and $1,2\text{ atm}$. It is crucial to maintain a low

leak rate to prevent the chamber from running out of oxygen, which is essential for bacteria to produce the violacein.

3.4 Testing

An essential part of the development of any fluidic system is the testing of every component and the entire unit together. For space applications, testing becomes even more important for the correct performance of the mission. In this respect, BIXO is not an exception. The absorbancy data extracted from the wells only give information about whether the bacteria mixed with the growth medium have reached the wells or not, how many wells it has reached and, of

Figure 29: 3D assembly of the manifold with attached pump, electrovalves and manifold-to-tube interfaces.

course, how the bacteria growth evolves, but if there is any problem in the rest of the system there is no way to know if it is related to the pump, the electrovalves, the chips or any other component. Ought to this fact, the only way to prevent errors from spoiling the whole biologic experiment is to intensively test each of the components alone and all of them together in launch and space conditions (i.e. temperature variations, random vibrations, etc.). Nevertheless, before even practising these simulated-ambient examinations it is much more relevant to perform basic functional tests, to make sure that the parts work as needed even in the best case scenario. Some functional tests performed are described below.

3.4.1 Microfluidic chip testing

So far, two batches of tests of the microfluidic chips have been executed to determine whether the air-retention problematic related to parallel branching of wells occurred on our cards. The first one was performed using microfluidic chips of admittedly flawed quality. The test simply consisted on pumping violet-dyed water along the inner channels of the

(a) SLA manifold

(b) SLS manifold

(c) FDM manifold

Figure 30: Three iterations of the manifold

LoCs in order to check all the wells were evenly filled. The process was executed with an air compressor that pushed the liquid at a pressure between 5 and 50 kPa.

After using four cards, three of them were perfectly filled. Nevertheless, the remaining one could not follow the same path because of a leakage caused by a defective sealant.

Figure 31: Microfluidic chip during the filling test.

Different results were achieved when the fluid inside the chips was removed and the filling was repeated. Both steps produced imperfect results; neither the emptying phase removed all the fluid nor the re-filling phase could expel all the air (Fig 32).

Figure 32: Microfluidic card after emptying (left) and after re-filling (right).

The second batch of experiments was performed with a pair of LoCs like the one in Figure 25 and the Takasago Peristaltic Pump (Figure 19). In this

case, the purpose of the test was to compare the two well distributions mentioned above (in parallel and in series) in order to determine which ended being more suitable.

The conclusions extracted by observing the flow through the inner channels and microwells of both LoCs were clear: wells connected in-series were filled without further complications and so did the parallel connected wells, however, these last were filled in different steps. When filling the first card, the wells on the sides of the parallel distribution were filled first and, just after they had finished, the central one was filled. For the second card, the filling of in-parallel wells started with one well placed at one side, then continued with the central one and finished with the one in the other side. In both cases, the flow did not circulated through any of the outlets of the wells until all of them were fully filled, indicating that no air would get stuck.

3.4.2 LoC Freezing testing

One microfluidic card of each of the two batches tested went below $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for a period of at least 24 h to simulate how these components would response in an undesirable scenario where the satellite cannot keep the temperature over $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The first batch was left to defrost for 15 minutes as it seemed enough for such a low volume of liquid, nevertheless, when pressure was again applied to the fluid, the sealant in the middle of both microfluidic layers started to peel off and an accumulation of dyed water was created in between (Figure 33).

The same test was repeated using the pair of fluidic chips from the second batch and leaving them a full hour to defrost, to ensure that no ice blocks were left inside. It was later observed that there was flow along both sets of serial wells but not so in the parallel distribution sets: in the first chip even flow was observed, whereas in the other one it only flowed through the central well.

3.4.3 Peristaltic pump testing

As for the testing of the peristaltic pump, a user interface was programmed to allow the regulation of

Figure 33: Accumulated dyed water inside a LoC due to inadequate defrost.

the speed of the pump from 0 to 50 RPM. The pump showed good response working in that range, but all the tests were performed at a speed between 30 and 50 RPM, since lower speeds delayed the process notably. However, it is still useful to count with low volume rates for precision-demanding situations. Regarding higher speed rates, the pump seemed to start malfunctioning when it was set over 50 RPM as it produced clicking noises due to inner parts slipping.

4 Challenges

Although the development of the BIXO fluidic system has suffered a notable boost in little time, there is still much work to be done in the future. Functional tests of critical components like the electrovalves, the check valves and the bacteria reservoirs have to be performed. Furthermore, space-like ambient and launch conditions tests have to be executed as well on every single part of the system.

Apart from that, further testing on microfluidic chips shall be performed to determine the optimal distribution of the wells and to examine the appearance of gas bubbles inside them as a consequence of long exposure to an atmospheric ambient. Flow simulations of the medium along the channels and through the serpentine shall also be executed to assess the efficiency of the bacteria mixing before reaching the wells.

In addition, the integration of the biological samples shall be studied to ensure the correct development of the experiment and to avoid contamination of the bacteria.

In conclusion, the iterative design-manufacture-test process has to be repeated constantly, adapting the system to mission changes, until reaching the optimal configuration. All of this while keeping track of the available budget of the mission and the deadlines for launching the satellite.

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References

- [1] A. Camanzo Mariño, M. Diz-Folgar, M. Vale-Xoubanova, P. Castro, P. Parafita, L. Amaro-

- Losada, F. Agelet, G. Bodelon, C. Sieiro, I. Pastoriza-Santos, and J. Pérez-Juste, “Bixo, a student-led cubesat mission for education and astrobiology research,” 02 2022.
- [2] C. Kitts, J. Hines, E. Agasid, A. Ricco, B. Yost, K. Ronzano, and J. Puig-Suari, “The genesat-1 microsatellite mission: A challenge in small satellite design,” 2006.
- [3] B. Harandi, S. Ng, L. C. Liddell, D. M. Gentry, and S. R. Santa Maria, “Fluidic-based instruments for space biology research in cubesats,” F. in *Space Technologies*, Ed., 2022.
- [4] N. Aeronautics and S. A. (NASA), *PharmaSat Fact Sheet*, 2009.
- [5] A. Ricco, M. Parra, D. Niesel, M. Piccini, D. Ly, M. McGinnis, A. Kudlicki, J. Hines, L. Timucin, C. Beasley, R. Ricks, M. McIntyre, C. Friedericks, M. Henschke, R. Leung, M. Diaz-Aguado, C. Kitts, I. Mas, M. Rasay, and B. Yost, *PharmaSat: Drug dose response in microgravity from a free-flying integrated biofluidic/optical culture-and-analysis satellite*, 02 2011, vol. 7929.
- [6] C. Kitts, K. Ronzano, R. Rasay, I. Mas, J. Acain, M. Neumann, L. Bica, P. Mahacek, G. Minelli, E. Beck, S. Li, B. Gamp, S. Agnew, J. Shepard, J. Hines, E. Agasid, C. Friedericks, M. Piccini, M. Parra, and M. McGinnis, *Initial Flight Results from the PharmaSat Biological Microsatellite Mission*, 01 2009.
- [7] G. Minelli, A. Ricco, C. Beasley, J. Hines, E. Agasid, B. Yost, D. Squires, C. Friedericks, M. Piccini, G. Defouw, M. McIntyre, R. Ricks, M. Parra, M. Diaz-Aguado, L. Timucin, M. Henschke, M. Lera, M. Tan, M. Cohen, and L. Bica, *O/OREOS Nanosatellite: A Multi-Payload Technology Demonstration*, 08 2010.
- [8] N. Aeronautics and S. A. (NASA), *SporeSat, Investigating the Gravitational Threshold for Calcium Ion Channel, Activation using a Nanosatellite Platform-Based*, 2013.
- [9] W. W. A. Wan Salim, J. H. Park, J. Rickus, A. Rademacher, A. Ricco, A. Schooley, J. Benton, B. Wickizer, A. Martinez, N. Mai, M. Rasay, D. Porterfield, L. Brownston, M. Cote, G. Defouw, M. Henschke, C. Kitts, E. Luzzi, M. Perez, and A. Sweet, *SPORE-SAT: A NANOSATELLITE PLATFORM LAB-ON-A-CHIP SYSTEM FOR INVESTIGATING GRAVITY THRESHOLD OF FERN SPORE SINGLE-CELL CALCIUM CURRENTS*, 05 2014, pp. 111–114.
- [10] M. R. Padgen, T. N. Chinn, C. R. Friedericks, M. P. Lera, M. Chin, M. P. Parra, M. E. Piccini, A. J. Ricco, and S. M. Spremo, *The EcAMSat fluidic system to study antibiotic resistance in low earth orbit: Development and lessons learned from space flight*, 2020, vol. 173, pp. 449–459. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S009457652030093X>
- [11] A. Matin, J.-H. Wang, M. Keyhan, R. Singh, M. Benoit, M. P. Parra, M. R. Padgen, A. J. Ricco, M. Chin, C. R. Friedericks, T. N. Chinn, A. Cohen, M. B. Henschke, T. V. Snyder, M. P. Lera, S. S. Ross, C. M. Mayberry, S. Choi, D. T. Wu, M. X. Tan, T. D. Boone, C. C. Beasley, M. E. Piccini, and S. M. Spremo, *Payload hardware and experimental protocol development to enable future testing of the effect of space microgravity on the resistance to gentamicin of uropathogenic Escherichia coli and its sigma s deficient mutant*, 2017, vol. 15, pp. 1–10. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2214552417300251>
- [12] S. Massaro Tieze, L. C. Liddell, S. R. Santa Maria, and S. Bhattacharya, *BioSentinel: A Biological CubeSat for Deep Space Exploration*, 0, vol. 0, no. 0, p. null, PMID: 32282239. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1089/ast.2019.2068>
- [13] M. Padgen, L. Liddell, S. Bhardwaj, D. Gentry, D. Marina, M. Parra, T. Boone, M. Tan,

- L. Ellingson, A. Rademacher, J. Benton, A. Schooley, A. Mousavi, C. Friedericks, R. Hanel, A. Ricco, S. Bhattacharya, and S. Santa Maria, *BioSentinel: A Biofluidic Nanosatellite Monitoring Microbial Growth and Activity in Deep Space*, 02 2021.
- [14] A. Arampatzis, A. Zaras, P. Matsatsos, O. Ousultzoglou, D. Nikolopoulou, E. Sandaltzoupoulou, C. Giannitsis, A. Theocharis, and E. Chatziargyriou, *Payload Design Definition and Justification File DDJF PL*, 2021.
- [15] A. Nygren and A. Ramm, *Microfluidics system for the MOREBAC astrobiology experiment module : Design of a cubesat module*, 2018.
- [16] *Cell Therapy Solutions*, 2022, p. 9. [Online]. Available: <https://www.celltherapy.saint-gobain.com>
- [17] *Model RP-Q Series Miniature Peristaltic Pump, DC Power, Discharge Flowrates to 3.0 ml/min*, Clark Solutions. [Online]. Available: <https://www.clarksol.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/RPQ1.pdf>
- [18] *ULTRA-MINIATURE LATCHING 2-PORT HIGH DENSITY INTERFACE (HDI) SOLENOID VALVE*, The Lee Company, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.theleeco.com/uploads/2021/11/PDS-135-2020-06-UltraMiniatureLatching2-PortHighDensityInterface-HDI-SolenoidValve.pdf>
- [19] *Technical Hydraulic Handbook*, The Lee Company, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ddp.nl/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Precision-Hydraulics-12th-Edition-2019.pdf>
- [20] *Catalogue mp6 accessories*, Bartels mikrotechnik, 2023. [Online]. Available: https://www.bartels-mikrotechnik.de/wp-content/uploads/simple-file-list/EN/Manuals-and-Data-Sheets/mp6_accessories_Catalogue.pdf
- [21] Y. Bessho, Y. Wang, K. Uesugi, and K. Morishima, *A venous valve-like check valve for microfluidic device*, 11 2018.
- [22] Elveflow. Microfluidic calculator. [Online]. Available: <https://www.elveflow.com/microfluidic-calculator/>
- [23] T. Daniel, S. White, and J. Lewis, *Chaotic mixing in three-dimensional microvascular networks fabricated by direct-write assembly*, 05 2003, vol. 2, pp. 265–71.